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Construction and exploration of the engineering education accreditation system with Chinese characteristics

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, China's engineering education has trained a large number of qualified talents for the development of China's economy and society, and has made due contributions to the global economy. Based on a brief introduction of the current development situation of China's engineering education, this research, firstly, systematically reviews the development process of China's engineering education accreditation system (CEEAS) from its start in 1992 to 2016; secondly, focuses on analysing institutional framework, accreditation standard and accreditation procedure of CEEAS; thirdly, emphasizes comparing the differences of engineering education accreditation system between China and the main contracting countries of the Washington Accord in order to analyse the existing problems of CEEAS; finally, reflects the problems existing in the construction of CEEAS.

Conference Key Areas: Quality Assurance and Accreditation; Sustainability and Engineering Education; Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Engineering education; Accreditation system; System construction; International mutual recognition; Washington Accord

INTRODUCTION

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China in 1949, engineering education has trained more than 20,000,000 engineering talents for China's industrialization and social economic development. As of 2015, 1,650 colleges and universities have

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set up engineering specialties, and the number of specialties reaches to 16,284. Engineering undergraduates have up to 5,247,000, accounting for about 33.3% of the total number of students at school. The rapid development of industrialization determines that China has a strong demand for engineering talents, and the number of graduates in colleges and universities in China is rapidly increasing. In terms of scale, China has a huge number of students in engineering education and has ranked the first in the world.

With the rapid expansion of scale and the higher standard of training quality of engineering talents, the existing engineering education quality assurance system is facing a severe test. On the other hand, with the development of economic globalization, the internationalization trend of engineering education is becoming clearer, and the transnational flow of engineering talents is also becoming more frequent. In this process, the educational and industrial sectors in China have recognized that it is necessary to establish China's engineering education accreditation system (CEEAS) with international substantial equivalence.

1 REVIEWING DEVELOPMENT HISTORY OF CEEAS

CEEAS launched a pilot project of the architectural accreditation in 1992, which has 15 years' development history. The former Ministry of Construction started a pilot scheme of 6 majors' accreditation in Tsinghua University, Tongji University, Tianjin University and Southeast University from 1992, and began to explore the practice of CEEAS(Fang 2013)..

In 2005, the State Council approved the establishment of the China Engineers System Reform and Coordination Group (CESRCG). The Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security is the head of the unit, and Chinese Academy of Engineering, Chinese Association for Science and Technology (CAST), the Ministry of Education is the deputy head of the unit. Three deputy heads of the unit are respectively responsible for the classification and design of the engineers system, external contact of accreditation and engineers, engineering education accreditation.

In 2007, after the approval of CESRCG, the Ministry of Education set up Experts Committee of China Engineering Education Accreditation (ECCEEA). With referring to the current international and domestic practice, ECCEEA formulated a set of guidance documents for CEEAS, including accreditation standard, accreditation procedure, accreditation policy etc. The ECCEEA worked until December 31, 2011, and the newly established China Engineering Education Accreditation Association (CEEAA) took over the accreditation work in 2012. In October 2015, CEEAA formally established, which was a national, non-profit, membership-based organization organized by more than 30 organizations and individuals. Under the leadership of the CAST, it is the only legal institution authorized by the Ministry of Education to carry out engineering education accreditation in China.

At the end of January 2013, China was accepted as a probationary member of the Washington Accord. In June 2016, China became the eighteenth formal member of the Washington Accord, which indicated that the quality standard of China's engineering education has basically achieved the international substantive equivalence and has been gradually recognized by international community.

2 THE CONSTRUCTION OF CEEAS

2.1 Institutional framework

CEEAA is responsible for the organization, implementation and management of China's engineering education accreditation. The association currently has 33 group members and some individual members. The group members cover the major trade and professional associations in engineering fields, and the individual members include the leaders and experts from government, universities, industry organizations and enterprises.

There is board of supervisors, council and secretariat under CEEAA. The council is the executive body of the association. The board of supervisors is responsible for overseeing the work of the council and the secretariat. The council includes Specialty Accreditation Committee (SAC), the Accreditation Conclusion and Review Committee (ACRC) and the Academic Committee (AC) (Figure 1). The SAC is the branch of CEEAA, which is established in accordance with the relevant professional fields. As of 2016, CEEAA has a total of 14 SAC, including mechanical, computer, chemical and pharmaceutical etc. The AC is responsible for formulating and revising accreditation standard and other accreditation documents, providing academic support for engineering education accreditation, and accrediting qualification for experts. The ACRC is responsible for considering accreditation report and accreditation conclusion made by the SAC and submitting the results to the council for approval.

Fig. 1. The framework of CEEAA

2.2 Accreditation standard

The accreditation standard is composed of two parts: general standard and supplementary standard. The general standard is consisted of seven elements: student, training objective, graduation requirements, continuous improvement, curriculum system, teachers and support condition. The supplementary standard specifies the special professional requirements and supplements of one or more areas (Table 1). It needs to be emphasized that: (1) The certification standard only contains 7 indicators, and 21 investigation points are just as the reference; (2) The supplementary standard is not a single index, but the content supplement that is not included in the general standard; (3) The training objective covers internationally

accepted 11 capability requirements of graduates and accords with result-oriented characteristic of the Washington Accord (ABET 2007).

Table 1. Accreditation standard and connotation interpretation

Type	Index	Investigation point
General standard	Training objective	Target evaluation and revision
		Graduate ability
	Curriculum system	Curriculum
		Practice link
		Thesis
	Teachers	Number and structure of teachers
		Teacher development
	Support condition	Teaching funds
		teaching facilities
		Teaching management and service
		Books
		Industry-university-research cooperation
	Students	Recruit students
		Student training and guidance
		Student employment
	Continuous improvement	Quality control of teaching process
		Graduates feedback
Graduation requirements	Theoretical knowledge	
	practical ability	
	Professional ethics	
	Lifelong learning	
Supplementary standard	Special requirements for each specialty	

2.3 Accreditation procedure

The process of accreditation is basically the same as that of most members of the Washington Accord, including 6 links: application and acceptance, school self-assessment, review of self-assessment report, on-the-spot investigation, accreditation conclusion, accreditation status's maintenance and improvement. Therefore, this study will no longer carry out specific discourse.

3 COMPARISON THE DIFFERENCES OF ACCREDITATION SYSTEMS

The core content of the Washington Accord is that the accreditation standard and procedure of each member are basically the same (Patil & Codner 2007). In order to achieve the objectives of the agreement, the institutional framework, accreditation standard and accreditation procedure developed by each member have shown great similarities. However, viewing the current practice, there are many differences between China and the main contracting countries of the Washington Accord. This study mainly analyses the differences from the cognition level, organization level, system level and practice level.

3.1 Cognition level

In the construction of engineering education accreditation system, the government, universities, industry and professional associations in the most contracting countries

of the Washington Accord have a high degree of acceptance. Taking the design of accreditation standard as an example, Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology of the United States (ABET) adopted the Engineering Criterion 2000 (EC 2000) in 1997, which realized the innovation of quality evaluation standard. In the design process of EC2000, the government, universities, industry and professional associations participate actively and play different functions. In the premise of full participation by all parties, accreditation system has a high acceptance and authority.

The design concept of CEEAS draws lessons from EC2000 and has maintained a high consistency with the Washington Accord (Han & Zhang 2015). However, the design of CEEAS is dominated by the government and the universities, and the industrial sectors are not effectively involved. Secondly, the phenomenon that emphasizes on the theoretical education and neglects the practical education in the process of students training in universities still exists, which leads that students' engineering practice ability is still not strong enough. The training of engineering talents in universities cannot fully meet the requirements of the industrial sectors (Zhu 2015), indirectly causing that the enthusiasm of the industry to participate in accreditation is not high. Overall, the acceptance of industrial sectors to CEEAS needs to be improved.

3.2 Organization level

Accreditation institutions in various countries have different development history, and the form is also unique. However, the development of accreditation institutions is closely linked with the social and economic development at that time. At the end of 1980s, with the needs to guarantee the quality of engineering education and the acceleration of economic globalization, accreditation has become an important function of engineering education organizations in various countries, and the emergence of international mutual recognition agreement on engineering education has also become inevitable. The Washington Accord was born under such a background.

Accreditation organizations of the main contracting countries of the Washington Accord are generally unofficial and independent institutions. For example, the ABET, established in 1932, is a non-governmental organization. As an organization of membership, ABET has a sound management mechanism and organizational structure with a high degree of independence and professionalism, and the authority of it is admitted by both the official and unofficial (Bi 2005). In contrast, China's accreditation organization has a big difference with ABET. The government plays a leading role in current accreditation organization, and it is involved in the work of the accreditation organization with the direct administrative means. Although the establishment of CEEAA promotes the independence and professionalism of accreditation organization, the official dominant colour still exists.

3.3 System level

The ultimate goal of the Washington Accord is to ensure that the graduates has professional qualifications in the field of their work after a certain period of time and continues to maintain and improve their vocational ability. Therefore, the effective convergence of accreditation system and engineer accreditation registration system is very important. At present, the accreditation institutions of the Washington Accord (such as Australia, Canada, Hong Kong, Ireland, New Zealand, Singapore, South Africa, Britain, Malaysia, Sri Lanka etc.) are comprehensive accreditation agencies, which are not only responsible for the accreditation of engineering education degree, but also the professional qualifications of engineers.

At present, excepting architecture or related majors, CEEAS is in a relatively isolated position, and failed to achieve effective convergence with engineer registration system. According to a survey, the enthusiasm of schools and students for accreditation begins to decrease, and many students think that their employment does not matter much with accreditation system. In addition, the industry is not very concerned about whether the school's specialty has passed the accreditation or not in the recruitment. This is largely due to lacking of effective convergence between accreditation system and engineer registration system.

3.4 Practice level

Compared with the main contracting countries of the Washington Accord, China has a large number of specialties that need to be certified and the scale of accreditation is growing too fast. Since 2006, the scale of China's accreditation has increased year by year, from 8 specialties in 2006 to 375 specialties in 2016, with an average annual growth rate of 46.9% (Figure 2). As of the end of 2016, China has certified 996 specialties, accounting for 6.1% of the total. Therefore, the future workload of accreditation is very large, which needs a huge and experienced team of experts.

Most members of the Washington Accord have a wealth of practical experience, encompassing a large number of experts with reasonable structure and high quality. Viewing the current practice, there are many problems in the quantity, structure and quality of China's accreditation team. At present, China's accreditation team only has about 600 people, which causing it is difficult to guarantee the accreditation quality in such a large workload. At the same time, the experts are mainly from the university's teachers and administrative staffs. They generally become a probationary expert through a simple training and become a formal expert through participation in an accreditation work. Therefore, a considerable number of experts lack accreditation experience and cannot have a good grasp of the concept, principle and standard of accreditation.

Fig. 2. Accreditation application scale and approval scale

4 REFLECTING THE PROBLEMS EXISTING IN CEEAS

4.1 Enhancing the acceptance of the industry

In the main contracting countries of the Washington Accord, the industry is actively involved in all aspects of accreditation and has a high degree of acceptance to its accreditation system. Therefore, China should strive to strengthen the contact with the industry and promote the industry to participate in the whole process of the CEEAS in order to effectively enhance the acceptance of the industry. Viewing the construction of accreditation bodies, China must formulate detailed working rules as

soon as possible in order to clearly define the functions of the industry and gradually form a sound internal operational mechanism of the association. Viewing the improvement of accreditation standard and practice, China should let engineers that have rich practical experience in industry fully participate in the accreditation work, and listen to their opinions and views, so as to enhance the industry acceptance to accreditation conclusion and even the whole accreditation system.

4.2 Building the completely independent and fair accreditation body

The prerequisite for the effective implementation of the accreditation system is the establishment of a fair, professional and standardized accreditation body. The organization responsible for accreditation is generally unofficial institution, such as the America's ABET, the United Kingdom's ECUK (Engineering Council UK), and the Japan's JABEE (Japan Accreditation Board for Engineering Education) etc. At present, CEEAS is still at the preliminary stage of practice and engineering education in China is very large and complex. If China completely imitates the western countries to use unofficial institutions for accreditation, it may not be able to ensure the effective management of accreditation and organizational work. In consideration of China's specific national conditions, China will gradually transform into a fully independent, fair accreditation body in a more mature stage. At the same time, in the process of constructing accreditation body, it is necessary to strengthen the mutual cooperation and make clear the division of functions among the government, universities and the industry, so as to improve the efficiency and quality of the accreditation work.

4.3 Promoting effective convergence between accreditation system and engineer registration system

Accreditation system and engineer registration system are interconnected and interactive. The main contracting countries of the Washington Accord have different practices in the implementation of the two jobs, but most of them have had a mature experience. Therefore, it is necessary for us to make further analysis and research on their experience, so as to provide reference for the reform of China's accreditation system and engineer registration system. From the view of future, Chinese effective way may be divided into two points. Firstly, China should set up the classification standard of engineering education and the qualification standard for engineers recognized by both the education and industry, in order to lay a good foundation for effective convergence between accreditation system and engineer registration system. Secondly, China should integrate the accreditation bodies and the engineer registration agencies into a system in order to simplify the organization, reduce operating costs, and effectively improve their work efficiency.

4.4 Building a large number of experts with reasonable structure and high quality

The effective implementation of accreditation work requires a high level of experts as a backup. In terms of the quantity, there are only about 600 people engaging in accreditation work in China. With respect to more than 16,000 specialties needed to be certified, the number of experts seems very lack. Therefore, it is necessary to appropriately increase the number of experts to meet the growing demand for accreditation. In terms of the structure, China's accreditation team is mainly composed by experts from universities. For example, when CEEAA organizes a field investigation, the experts group generally has 5 people, but only 1 people are from the industry. Therefore, China should improve the proportion of experts from the industry in order to truly evaluate the quality of engineering education from the

perspective of users. In terms of the quality, China should strengthen the training of experts in the accreditation concept, standard and procedure etc. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen the professional ethics training of experts, so as to improve the impartiality of accreditation.

5 CONCLUSION

After 15 years of development, CEEAS has established a sound accreditation body, accreditation standard and accreditation procedure under the guidance of the Washington Agreement. However compared with the major signatory countries of the Washington Agreement, CEEAS still have some problems and challenges at the cognition level, organization level, system level and practice level. Therefore in the future development of CEEAS, it is necessary to strengthen ties with the industrial sectors and strive to enhance the acceptance of the industry; reduce the direct intervention of government and gradually build a completely independent, fair accreditation body; promote effective convergence between accreditation system and engineer registration system; build a large number of experts with reasonable structure and high quality etc. At the same time, for the actual development of China's engineering education, the number of universities is large, the level of running school is not uniform, and the demand for engineering talents from industries is also different. Therefore, under the premise of maintaining the certification standards and quality standards required by the Washington Agreement, it is necessary for us to think deeply and continue to practice how to maintain the local characteristics of CEEAS.

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